

THE INFLUENCE OF L1 (GERMAN) IN LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE.

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ELSEVIER

Sanjar Kurbanov Saliyevich

Bukhara State University
English Linguistics Department

Abstract: Interference happens frequently in foreign language education, and the teacher should be directed by the actualization regularities of linguistic systems in the minds of the students. Overcoming the interfering influence of the native language requires a thorough understanding of all native and learnt language aspects in comparison plan. The article discusses the role and significance of first (whose major language is German) language interference in foreign (English) language instruction. It covers the many varieties of interference from a linguistic and didactic standpoint. The author presents his experience, observations, and research on native language interference in teaching English as a foreign language to future native language teachers, as well as the most common errors in students' speech and techniques for correcting them.

Keywords: Interference, positive transfer, negative transfer, interferential mistake

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About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

Abstract: Интерференция в иноязычном обучении встречается часто, и преподаватель должен ориентироваться на закономерности актуализации языковых систем в сознании учащихся. Преодоление мешающего влияния родного языка требует глубокого понимания всех аспектов родного и изученного языка в плане сравнения. В статье рассматриваются роль и значение первого (основным языком которого является немецкий) языкового вмешательства в обучение иностранному (английскому) языку. Он охватывает множество разновидностей интерференции с лингвистической и дидактической точек зрения. Автор представляет свой опыт, наблюдения и исследования о вмешательстве родного языка в преподавание английского языка как иностранного будущим учителям-носителям языка, а также о наиболее распространенных ошибках в речи учащихся и способах их исправления.

Keywords: Интерференция, положительный перенос, отрицательный перенос, интерференционная ошибка

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Abstract: Chet tilini o'qitishda aralashuv tez-tez sodir bo'ladi va o'qituvchi talabalar ongida til tizimlarining aktualizatsiya qonuniyatlariga yo'naltirilishi kerak. Ona tilining aralashuvchi ta'sirini bartaraf etish uchun taqqoslash rejasida ona tili va o'rganilgan tilning barcha jihatlarini to'liq tushunish kerak. Maqolada chet (ingliz) tilini o'qitishda birinchi (asosiy tili nemis tili) til interferentsiyasining roli va ahamiyati muhokama qilinadi. U lingvistik va didaktik nuqtai nazardan aralashuvning ko'p turlarini qamrab oladi. Muallif bo'lajak ona tili o'qituvchilariga ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida o'rgatishda ona tilining aralashuvi bo'yicha o'z tajribasi, kuzatishlari va tadqiqotlarini, shuningdek, o'quvchilar nutqidagi eng ko'p uchraydigan xatolar va ularni tuzatish usullarini taqdim etadi.

Keywords: Interferentsiya, salbiy ta'sir, ijobiy ta'sir, Interferentsial xato

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The mother tongue has always had an impact on how people learn foreign languages, among other conditions and influences. Translating from one language into another is essentially inevitable when studying a foreign tongue. Students tend

to to simply translate concepts or structures into English rather than resorting to their native language's grammatical system and using those they are familiar with. This invariably results in lexical and grammatical interference mistakes.

As an English teacher, I had to deal with mistakes made by students on a daily basis. I taught English at Bukhara State University in Uzbekistan, and I saw a variety of errors made by German philology students (Uzbek students) learning English as a second language. To gain a better understanding of this issue and to assist Uzbek students in eliminating these errors, I decided to conduct this research and discover which spheres of language are typically affected by language transfer in the German and English languages.

Language interference is a phenomenon in which a learner's mother tongue influences their acquisition of a second language. Interference is defined as "transfer" by Ellis as "the impact that the learner's L1 exerts over the acquisition of an L2." Interference is defined by Lott as "errors in the learner's usage of the foreign language that can be traced back to the mother tongue." According to Dulay et al., the contrastive analysis hypothesis states that if structures in the L1 differ from those in the L2, errors reflecting the structure of the L1 may be produced. Coming up from above given, it is possible to say that significant researches have been conducted in this sector of expertise over the years.

There are different understandings about whether the phenomenon of language interference is mistake or not. While some linguists consider interference as a mistake, others point out that it is just a lack of L2 knowledge of a language learners. Ellis, for instance, distinguishes between errors and mistakes, referring to errors as gaps in the learner's knowledge caused by the learner's inability to determine what is correct. Errors, on the other hand, show occasional gaps in language output. According to Dulay et al., transfer can be of two types: "negative" and "positive." While using L1 knowledge to acquire a second language is considered "negative transfer," there can be instances of "positive transfer" that result in the automatic correct usage of the L1 structure in second language output where the structures in both languages are the same (Dulay et al.).

Example: Negative transfer and Positive transfer

These examples show that between English and Russian sentence structure, in most situation, words match with the translation, while between English and Uzbek there is a huge difference in a word order. That draws to the Idea that in most case learners from Russian speaking countries acquire the language much faster than Uzbek students do. Now it would be better to compare English with German languages in order to have clear view why (uzbek) students whose major is German face difficulties with learning English language.

Though the two languages belong to the same language family they have numerous differences rather than similarities. In the examples above it is obvious that when the modal verbs used in the sentence (German) the main verb is put at the end of the sentence, while in English the main verb always follows a modal verb. In the following example we remove the modal verb and see how the word order changes.

Bhela proceeds the idea, and states that it depends on the relationship between the two languages in question. Languages having more similar structures (for example, English and Russian) are more vulnerable to mutual influence than languages with fewer similarities. Nonetheless, it may be claimed that the greater the distance between L1 and L2, (English and Uzbek) the more probable learning challenges will arise because the learner will find it difficult to understand and employ completely new language structures.

Michael Swan presents a more detailed categorization of areas touched by language transfer while studying English as a second language. He focuses on:

- **phonology:** vowels, consonants, stress, intonation, and juncture;
- **orthography and punctuation:** spelling and punctuation;
- **vocabulary:** false friends, word formation, and pairs of contrasting words;
- **grammar:** interrogative and negative structures, auxiliaries, time, tense, and aspect, conditionals, modal verbs, passivisation, non-finite forms, word

However, Richards contends that not all errors produced by second language learners can be traced only to first language transfer. He proposes that learners build knowledge of target language structures in a manner comparable to that of young first language learners. He distinguishes between intralingual and developmental mistakes for this purpose. The intralingual mistake includes difficulties such as incorrect generalization, incomplete rule application, or failure to learn how specific rules are applied. Developmental errors, on the other hand, demonstrate ideas such as over-generalization, ignorance, rule constraints, and insufficient rule application.

Ex. English to Russian

Yesterday I *spoke to* my English teacher. – Вчера я говорил *с* преподавателем. Ich habe *mit* meinem Englischlehrer gesprochen.

You must *speak with* confidence. – Тебе надо говорить *с* уверенностью. Sie müssen *mit* Zuversicht sprechen.

In these two sentences the verb “to speak” is used with different prepositions. However, the translation gives us the same meaning and the use of the same preposition which is also one of the obstacles that confuse students while speaking in English.

The effect of the native language (whose major language is German) on the learned (English) language has always been an integral part of consciousness. It doesn't turn out explicitly and systematically but often serves as initiating agent of negative effect and in the result of unconscious spontaneous transfer of language habit. Hereupon there occurs abnormality of foreign language under the effect of foreign language which is interference, that can be realized in all levels of language system but the grammar interference causes the greatest number of mistakes. The

reason is that that the interacting systems with unequal grammar features and categories are complex enough and impede speech production in foreign language. The type of interference and its degree of intense are determined by different factors, particularly: specific conditions of language contacts, structure of languages and the age of learners.

If we compare all definitions to language interference, we can notice, that one type of scientists considers language interference that results in divergence in the norm at least of one contacting languages; the others define it as the transfer of speech habits. The first definition is linguistic, the second one is psychological. U.Yusupov agrees that the linguistic definition stresses on the language as an abstract system, and the psychological one underlines the language as speech activity. Although the both definitions are correct, they need completion.

To sum up, the future teacher of English as a foreign language should not only be fluent in the language, understand its structure deeply and correctly from a linguistic point of view, but also clearly understand those aspects of the English language that bring this language closer and, on the contrary, distinguish it from the native (German) student, and know the interference potential of interlingual differences, interlingual interference results and ways to overcome them.

REFERENCES:

1. Bhela, Baljit. "Native Language Interference in Learning a Second Language: Exploratory case studies of native language interference with target language usage." *International Education Journal*, vol. 1, pp. 22-31. 1999.
2. Dulay, Heidi, et al. *Language Two*. Oxford University Press, 1982.
3. Ellis, Rod. *Second Language Acquisition*. Oxford University Press, 1997
4. Erkinovna, Y. F. Negative Politeness. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(6), 1249-1255. <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/344146-negative-politeness-c55f7abc.pdf>.
5. G. Ya. Tojiyeva Native language interference in teaching English Uzbek students. ISSN: 1533-7812 Vol-21-Issue-05-May-2020
6. Kurbanov, S. (2022). МЕСТО КРИТИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ МЕТОДАХ ОБУЩЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 18(18). извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/7427
7. Lott, David. "Analysing and Counteracting Interference Errors." *ELT Journal*, vol. 37/3, pp. 256-261. 1983.

8. Richards, Jack C. Error Analysis: Perspectives on Second Language Acquisition. Longman, 1974
9. Saparova, M. R. (2019). PRINCIPLES OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING. In Язык и культура (pp. 60-67). <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=42528624>
10. Kurbanov, S. S., & Saparova, M. R. (2021). BADIY ASAR JOZIBADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA QARG'ISH ANGLATUVCHI DISFEMIZMLARNING PERSONAJLAR NUTQIDA BERILISHI. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(4), 1246-1251. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/badiiy-asar-jozibadorligini-oshirishda-qarg-ish-anglatuvchi-disfemizmlarning-personajlar-nutqida-berilishi>
11. Saparova, M. R. (2016). The problem of stylistic classification of colloquial vocabulary. Міжнародний науковий журнал, (5 (1)), 80-82. <https://www.inter-nauka.com/uploads/public/1505892674749.pdf#page=81>
12. Saparova, M. (2022). Xolid Husayniyning "Ming Quyosh Shu'lası" (A Thousand Splendid Suns) asarida qo'llanilgan yuklamalarning o'zbek va ingliz tillaridagi leksik-semantik va grammatik xususiyatlari. *Центр Научных Публикаций (Buxdu.Uz)*, 18(18). [Http://Journal.Buxdu.Uz/Index.Php/Journals_Buxdu/Article/View/7312](http://Journal.Buxdu.Uz/Index.Php/Journals_Buxdu/Article/View/7312)
13. Yuldasheva Feruza Erkinovna. (2021). POLITENESS MARKERS IN SPOKENLANGUAGE. Euro-Asia Conferences, 37-40. Retrieved from <http://papers.euroasiaconference.com/index.php/eac/article/view/528>.
14. Yuldasheva, F. (2021). The Expression of Politeness Category in The Uzbek And English Languages. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 1(1). извлечено от
http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/2835
15. Yusupov U.K. Theoretical bases of comparative linguistics. Tashkent: Fan. 2007. - 126 p.